

THE SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF A COMPOUND WORD IN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article highlights about the semantic structure of compound words and the motivation of a compound word, the relationship between the components of a compound word, the types of meanings and their interaction. Also we analyzed several words and observed views of famous scholars about the compound words.

Keywords: compound words, reality, structure, concept of motivation, figurative meaning, categorical meaning.

Main problem

In English, reduplication is traditionally considered within the framework of composition. As I.V. Arnold writes: "some combinations that may be called compounds by right of pattern, as they very markedly consist of two parts" (Arnold 1986, 129), while indicating their differences "in most cases they fail to satisfy the definition of a compound word". In order to visualize these differences more clearly, let us consider the nature of the compound word in more detail.

Analyses and research problems

A compound word, in general, also has common features of a derivative word: secondary, structural and semantic motivation. In Russian linguistics, a compound word is understood as a lexical whole, having a structural and semantic unity, distinguished by the integrity of semantics. It is formed from two, less often three existing full-value bases, and as a rule, the value of the newly formed whole becomes not identical to the sum of its parts (Amosova, 1956, 68). Compound words, like all derivatives, are characterized by motivation - "such an organization of its component that allows you to reveal its denotative meaning by referring to the lexical meaning of each of the components and their logical and subject relationship" (Meshkov, 1988, 18-19). O.D. Meshkov believes that in complex words one should distinguish between structural-semantic and lexical motivation. The first is related to the ability to correlate the semantic structure of a compound word with a parallel syntactic construction, based on the semantic interaction of the components. Lexical motivation is associated with the use of component words in their direct meaning (Meshkov, 1988).

Within the framework of a compound word, full-valued stems enter into certain semantic relations, two meanings are integrated, two categorical meanings interact. The addition of the aggregate value of the composite occurs in different ways. An extreme case is the non-derivation of the meaning of language education from the totality of its constituent parts, defined by A.I. Smirnitsky as idiomatic. Compound words are also characterized by semantic integrity, "emphasizing that a given object or phenomenon is thought of as something one, a special whole, even if the complexity of the structure of the word denoting it is noted" (Smirnitsky, 1952).

A compound word as an object of study attracted the attention of many scientists. The issues of delimitation of compound words and phrases were studied, the patterns of constructing structural-semantic models of

compound words, the features of their semantics were studied. The studies carried out in this direction note the fact that the English language is characterized by the widespread use of an extensive system of word-formation means, a tendency to express thoughts within a single word, which has "much greater meaningful and expressive possibilities than a phrase". Linguists propose to describe the total content transmitted by the composite through the categories of semantic-stylistic capacity, which help to reveal the depth of the word, its expressive possibilities (Andryukhina 1987; Dyuzhikova 1990)

Main part: Materials and methods

The meaning of a compound word is, first of all, what allows it to mean one or another object of reality, and for the perceiver to correlate the compound word with a certain object of reality. Analysis of the semantic structure of a compound word consists in clarifying these conditions. The main difficulty of this analysis is connected with the fact that a compound word, being, like any word, addressed to the world of things. "At the same time addressed to the world of words" i.e. is motivated. On the other hand, this motivation itself is implicit in a compound word, this inconsistency of the semantic structure of a compound word - addressing both the world of things and the world of words - as well as implicit motivation and makes the analysis of the semantic structure of a compound word a difficult problem in which the following can be distinguished main elements: the motivation of a compound word, the relationship between the components of a compound word, the types of meanings of a compound word and their interaction, the polysemy of a compound word, the idiom of a compound word, the homonymy of a compound word.

To understand the semantic structure of a compound word, the concept of structural motivation is of paramount importance, that is, the structural-semantic interaction of the parts of a compound word that forms the denotative, lexical meaning of the word. Since such interaction is predetermined by the meaning, the semantics of the parts of a compound word, then the structural-semantic motivation is nothing but the structural-semantic meaning of the compound word. If we rely on the definition of O.S. Akhmanova the concept of "motivated", then a motivated compound word - which is more or less directly correlated with the phrase that conveys its content, i.e. meaning. The application of this concept in its simplest form obviously means that the word home-made (made at home) is motivated,

and the word *house-broken* (trained to live in a house) is unmotivated. In general terms, such a concept of motivation/unmotivation of a compound word is quite acceptable. However, one should pay attention to the fact that in the case of *home-made* the word has developed a figurative meaning in which the first component is desemantized, cf. *special dish of this restaurant is home-made noodles*

Lexical motivation: *home-made* no longer means made at home, but obviously means “sort, type of dish”. As for specific lexical meanings, their relationship with the category of motivation is also very complex and cannot be schematized, but is the factors of each given word. For example, the words *field-dog*, *house-dog*, *sweater-girl*, *cat-bird*. In the first two, motivation is manifested, since the objects designated by their components are in conceivable, predictable logical-subject relationships: *field / dog = dogs in the field*; *house / dog = dog in the house*, i.e. The logical relationship between a place and an object is that the object is located in a certain place. This is the structural-semantic motivated meaning of these compound words.

Results

Numerous compound words are included in the category of object-motivated compound words; principles of categorical meaning are not found in the semantic structure. In such cases, the logical-objective connection between the components is established based on the direct objective meaning of the bases of the components, for example, *eye wrinkle*, *hat band*, *knee breeches*. The meaning of all these words is easily perceived, although none of them can be analyzed from the standpoint of categorically motivated relations. So *knee breeches* are *knee-length trousers*, i.e. the word *knee* appears in the meaning of a measure of length. In subject-motivated compound words, the semantic structure is established as a result of reflecting the logical-subject interaction that exists between objects in the real world.

With the development of complex words of ambiguity, its figurative meaning becomes idiomatic in a purely lexical understanding. When analyzing the idiomaticity of a compound word, one should distinguish between the original and acquired idiomaticity of compound words with initial idiomaticity - these are words that are idiomatic at the time of formation and never act in a non-idiomatic sense. So, *gate-crasher* means only an uninvited guest, a spectator without a ticket, and does not mean the one who breaks the gate that such a person does not exist in principle.

Indeed, the ambiguity i.e. the acquired idiomaticity of a compound word is in the sphere of lexical and not derivational analysis, because the change in the meaning of a compound word is fundamentally not related to its structure of a compound word.

If lexical idiomaticity can act in parallel with a transparent syntactic structure, then the opposite phenomenon also takes place: the use of complex components in their direct, non-portable, non-idiomatic meaning can be “in the grid” of structural idiomaticity. Let's explain this with an example. In the compound word *bird-stone*, both the first and second components appear in their direct meaning - a *bird-stone*, however, the meaning of the most complex word is not clear to us,

because we do not know, we do not know the semantic relationship of these parts.

Conclusion

1. At the present stage in linguistics, a cognitive approach to language is developing and it is considered as a means of conceptualizing reality by the embodiment of a linguistic picture of the world, which pre-determines the perception of human reality - perception through “through the prism of language”. The communicative act is considered as a means of achieving a certain personally significant goal. The path to solving an extralinguistic goal is sculpted through an adequate selection and arrangement of linguistic material for the most complete expression of one's intention in given situational conditions.

2. Language as a functional system is a set of full-valued nominative units. The nominative arsenal of a language is the whole set of units that have a nominative function to designate individual fragments of an extralinguistic continuum corresponding to the vision of the world by a given linguo-cultural community.

3. Along with the classical type of nominative units, non-significant vocabulary plays a certain role. These include reduplicative words

4. Compounding is an important means of replenishing the vocabulary and an important link in the nominative system of the language. A compound word is an object of study for many scientists. The criterion for selecting a compound word does not always work successfully. Structurally, compound words are motivated signs. From a semantic point of view, one can distinguish subject-motivated and subject-non-motivated words.

5. A study of the literature on the problem of reduplication revealed the fact that it is a universal phenomenon in many languages of the world. However, linguistics has not developed a unified interpretation of this phenomenon. Reduplication is the doubling of the stem of a word by speech requirement, by stylistic and communicative necessity, the repetition of the same word to express the quantitative plurality of a phenomenon, object or process, exaggeration (excessiveness), united around one concept, action or circumstance.

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